

A TOOL FOR IDENTIFYING FOREST AREAS IN EUROPE EXPOSED TO SYSTEMATIC STRESS DUE TO CLIMATE CHANGE

Forests are complex systems and their interaction with and response to climate change are very difficult to predict. Therefore, we use historical and current trends in forest biomass and productivity across Europe to identify areas at risk of natural disturbances or even forest loss. Photosynthesis and growth trends are obtained from well-established models and satellite measurements.

Forest Monitoring

GEOGRAPHICAL LOCATION

We divide Europe into 1 km² grid cells and calculate the gross primary production (GPP) for each cell every month. GPP is the amount of photosynthetically derived chemical energy that fuels the build-up of carbon-based biomass created by primary producers in a given time interval. Some of this energy is used by plants for cellular respiration and maintaining existing tissues, while the rest is used for biomass accumulation through tree growth and reproduction.

We provide a tool based on moving time averages that can be used to identify any irregularities in primary productivity, and consequently in biomass development, over time in any square kilometre area across Europe. The tool will filter out and identify areas affected by climate change, which in concrete terms is related to intensive droughts, forest fires, and similar stress conditions.

This tool will be helpful for foresters and wood industry stakeholders because it will enable them to identify whether their areas of interest are affected by climatic and environmental stressors. They can then determine the degree of stress and decide how to mitigate it and improve forest productivity.

Level maps of gross primary production collected over a long period of time are analysed and transformed pixel by pixel in order to identify the frequency of forest changes or disturbances, and to evaluate the risk of low productivity across Europe. The main source of the GPP data is the Sentinel-5P satellite, and this data is also compared to that generated by models.

Forest changes

Sentinel 5P

GPP levels